

KBR **Where time
is treasured**

ISNI, a global identifier fit for research beyond borders

KBR (Royal Library of Belgium)

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What is ISNI?

International Standard
Name Identifier

the ISO certified global **standard**
that uniquely identifies **public identities**
who contributed to **creative works**

EN Philip, Duke of Burgundy
FR Philippe III

NL Filips de Goede
ES Felipe III Duque de Borgoña

0000 0001 0837 5753

<https://isni.org/isni/0000000108375753>

KBR, an ISNI registration agency

Interaction with the ISNI database

1. Bulk load submission

- to match legacy records with ISNI database
- assignment of 470,811 ISNIs to KBR records

2. via API

- monthly request of new ISNIs

3. via WebInterface

- manual data curation

Trigger: monitor legal deposit

Legal deposit – Challenges

Monitoring legal deposit is particularly challenging in Belgium for two reasons:

1. Belgian ‘national’ heritage is located on the crossroads of at least three language communities

.be

Vlaamse overheid	NL
FÉDÉRATION WALLONIE-BRUXELLES	FR
DG.be	DE

Legal deposit – Challenges

2. Belgian legal deposit legislation includes all printed works:

not only published in **Belgium**;

▶ Belgian **publisher** is required to deposit

but also published **abroad**, and written by a Belgian author who is domiciled in Belgium.

▶ Belgian **author** is required to deposit

Legal deposit – Needs

Due to these challenges, KBR has two major needs in order to efficiently monitor legal deposit:

1. gather **dispersed** and **multilingual** info from diverse and often siloed sources;
2. track and trace **‘Belgian’ publications** anywhere in the world or translated in any language.

Legal deposit – Solutions

With the aim of swiftly retrieving and integrating quality information on Belgian authors and their publications from different data sources, two solutions are very helpful:

International Standard Name Identifier

= persistent, language-neutral, machine readable identifier for contributors to creative works

Linked Data to combine bibliographic & authority data from different sources

Research programme: BRAIN-be

Partners: KBR & KU Leuven & UCLouvain

Info: <https://www.kbr.be/en/projects/beltrans/>

<https://github.com/kbrbe/beltrans-data-integration>

Poster: <https://zenodo.org/record/7976749>

Financed by

Intra-Belgian literary translations since 1970

- intra-Belgian author / illustrator / scenarist / publishing director
- location published anywhere in the world
- literary literary genres (novel, youth literature, comics, poetry)
literary non-fiction (mainly history books)
- translations FR-NL / NL-FR
- time-period 1970-2020

Find translations in different sources

different formats / quality / datafields
large data dumps
query via API

Integrate data by interlinking it

International Standard Book Number

- > to find and link book editions
- > using ISBN10 and ISBN13

International Standard Name Identifier

- > to find and link contributors
- > to enrich KBR person records with nationality

Filter on Belgian contributor(s)

created by

Without ISNI: manual integration

Without ISNI we have to solve manually all kind of name issues:

- ▶ **homonyms** Van Hecke, Geert journalist ≠ chef-kok
- ▶ **duplicates** check same names and merge duplicates
- ▶ **name variants** Lange, Bob de = De Lange, Bob
- ▶ **pseudonyms** distinguish and link pseudonyms ≈ real names

Integrated data from main sources

KBR

{BnF

7,531 contributors
75% with ISNI

6,761

1,835

Based on corpus
d.d. 2023-05-05

3,984

KB

1,241

CAMille

Centre d'archives sur les médias et l'information
Centrum voor Archieven over Media en Informatie

Partners: KBR & ULB

FEDt-WIN researcher: Brecht Deseure

volunteer at KBR: Sergio Alonso Mislata

Info: <https://www.kbr.be/en/projects/camille/>

Financed by

Scope

- Goal develop a database of Belgian journalists and media since 1830
- Priorities 1 persons [2 media: written press, radio, television]
- Nationality Belgian OR any nationality but related to Belgian media
- Location published in Belgium OR abroad but created by a Belgian journalist
- Language any
- Time-period 1830 to present

Find journalists in different sources

different formats / quality / datafields
query via API or catalogue search

Printed sources,
less structured

Search criteria in 4 digital sources

Keyword “*journalist*”

Nationalities Belgium, Netherlands, France,
Luxembourg, Germany, UK, Switzerland, Canada
= first selection, to be reviewed and completed

1 by keyword "journalist"

ca. 1K hits

2 search by ISNIs found at BnF, Wikidata, KB

ca. 7,5K hits

Autorités KBR

Nouvelle recherche | Recherche mémorisée | Historique de recherche

PARAMÈTRES DE LA RECHERCHE

Partout

TOUT="*journalist*"

Partout = *journalist*

RÉSULTATS (982)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Type de notice	Forme autorisée	Date	KBR - ISNI	Sexe	Documents liés ↓
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personne physique	Dufaux, Jean (1949-....) (Scénariste de bande dessinée, jo...	1949-....	ISNI 0000 0001 2135 636...	M	734
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personne physique	van Oudheusden, Pieter (1957-2013) (Nederlands schrijv...	1957-2013	ISNI 0000 0000 0299 907...	M	462
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personne physique	Couvreur, Daniel (19..-) (Journaliste)	19..-	ISNI 0000 0000 0110 4849	M	380
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personne physique	Kipling, Rudyard (1865-1936) (écrivain, journaliste)	1865-1936	ISNI 0000 0001 2098 9213	M	348
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personne physique	Colette (1873-1954) (Romancière, actrice et journaliste)	1873-1954	ISNI 0000 0001 2138 005...	F	319
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personne physique	Gille, Philippe (1831-1901) (Journaliste, librettiste d'opéra...	1831-1901	ISNI 0000 0001 1054 9994	M	267

{ BnF ca. 28K hits (in 2022)

{ BnF Catalogue général

[Recherche avancée](#)

[AUTEURS A-Z](#)

[SUJETS A-Z](#)

[PÉRIODIQUES](#)

[COTE](#)

[NOTICES D'AUTORITÉ !\[\]\(e82bb7a73cab40c77fe69a7e55ffd735_img.jpg\)](#)

[DANS UNIVERS !\[\]\(868cd8bec65c3e41dda30683af45e20b_img.jpg\)](#)

[Accueil](#) > [Recherche notices d'autorité](#) > [Liste de notices d'autorité](#)

29 125 Notices d'autorité

 Ajouter à mes références (0)

Tri par : [Défaut](#)

1 sur 1 457

20 résultats/page

<input type="checkbox"/> 1	Hirsch, Mario Politologue Personne	19..
<input type="checkbox"/> 2	Braun, Josy (1938-....) Romancier Personne	1938
<input type="checkbox"/> 3	Vallenthini, Michèle Docteure en littérature Personne	19..

VOTRE RECHERCHE

Recherche avancée dans les notices d'autorité

→ ET Toute la notice : journaliste / Tous les mots

→ ET Statut : Notice de référence

→ ET Pays Allemagne / Allemagne (République fédérale). / Belgique / Canada / Confédération helvétique. / France / Grande-Bretagne / Luxembourg / Pays-Bas / Royaume-Uni. / Suisse

[Modifier votre recherche](#)

RÉCUPÉRER LES NOTICES

Ma sélection (0)

 Télécharger/Imprimer

 Envoyer par courriel

 Exporter dans un tableau

 Transférer pour un SGB

Tous les résultats (29 125)

 Exporter dans un tableau

 Transférer pour un SGB

ca. 23K unique hits, several nationalities

Wikidata Query Service

Examples

Help

More tools

Query Builder


```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?countryLabel ?date_of_birth ?date_of_death ?place_of_birthLabel ?place_of_deathLabel
2 ?isni ?NTA ?BnF ?genderLabel ?native_languageLabel ?languages_writtenLabel
3 WHERE {
4   ?item wdt:P106 wd:Q1930187;
5         wdt:P27 ?country.
6   FILTER(?country IN (wd:Q31, wd:Q142, wd:Q55))
7 SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],fr,nl,en". }
8   OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P569 ?date_of_birth.}
9   OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P570 ?date_of_death.}
10  OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P19 ?place_of_birth.}
11  OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P20 ?place_of_death.}
12  OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P213 ?isni.}
13  OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P1006 ?NTA.}
14  OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P268 ?BnF.}
15  OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P21 ?gender.}
16  OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P103 ?native_language.}
17  OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P1412 ?languages_written.}
18 }
19
```


5518 unique KB URIs, of which 130 identified as Belgian

Default Data Set Name (Graph IRI)

Query Text

```
sselect * where {
?s schema:mainEntityOfPage/schema:isPartOf <http://data.bibliotheken.nl/id/dataset/persons> .
?s schema:description ?d .
?d bif:contains "'journalist*'" .

optional { ?s rdfs:label ?label. }
optional { ?s schema:familyName ?familyName.}
optional { ?s schema:givenName ?givenName.}
optional { ?s schema:name ?fullName .}
optional { ?s schema:birthDate ?birthDate.}
optional { ?s schema:deathDate ?deathDate.}
optional { ?s schema:nationality ?nationality .}
optional { ?s schema:sameAs ?isni .}
}
```


Integrated data from main sources

50,645
journalists
73% with ISNI

Based on corpus
d.d. 2023-02-06,
including smaller sources

Work in progress

KBR

7,551

BnF

26,418

23,193

KB

745

Only

From the Belgian Bibliography ...

**... towards linked data
on Belgian entities**

From the Belgian Bibliography ...

- **1837** **Foundation of Royal Library of Belgium**
mandate to publish a Bibliography of Belgium
- **1875 – 1997** **Printed periodical** (subscription)
1966: Enactment of legal deposit legislation
> more accurate reflection of national production
- **1998 – present** **Online publication** (free of charge)
monthly pdf's on [Bibliography of Belgium](#)
exportable records in [online catalogue](#) (EN-FR-NL)

... towards linked data on Belgian entities

Library catalogue

- ↳ Documents
- ↳ Authorities

Limited approach

Locked in library domain

versus

Semantic web

- ↳ Use HTTP URIs
- ↳ Standardised info (e.g. RDF)

Any approach possible

Linking silos and domains

Authors in KBR-catalogue

WWW.KBR.BE

General catalog

Belgica

BelgicaPress

BelgicaPeriodicals

KBR

General catalog

Collections ▾

Authors ▾

AUTHORS - PERSONS ▾

de goede, filips

×

+ advanced search

Philippe le Bon

See linked records

Titre(s)	Duc de Bourgogne
Data	r. 1419-1467
Website	https://bibale.irht.cnrs.fr/1570
ISNI	isni 0000 0001 0837 5753
Name variants	Filips de Goede Philip the Good Philipp der Gute Filippo III di Borgogna Felipe III de Borgoña

[Found an error or
problem?](#)

[Permalink](#)

KBR authors (with ISNI) in Wikidata

KBR person ID

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P11249>

The screenshot shows the Wikidata Query Service interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Wikidata logo, the text "Wikidata Query Service", and buttons for "Examples", "Help", "More tools", and "Query Builder". Below the navigation bar, there is a SPARQL query editor with a light blue background. The query is as follows:

```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?KBR_ID ?ISNI WHERE {  
2   ?item wdt:P11249 ?KBR_ID  
3   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE]". }  
4   OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P213 ?ISNI.}  
5 }
```

Short URL to query: <https://w.wiki/6nGo>

177898 results in 56723 ms

MetaBelgica

Partners: **KBR**

Royal Library of Belgium

Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium

Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage

Royal Museums of Art and History

Goal: a shared entity management infrastructure

between Federal Scientific Institutions

MetaBelgica

What?

- Person Authorities
- Organisation Authorities
- Time/Events
- Locations

Enriched data I

Enriched data II

Extract Transform Load

Human and machine interfaces

Takeaway

**use ISNI for research
on creative persons**

ISNI, fit for research beyond borders

BELTRANS

1. filter on Belgian nationality

CAMille

2. bridge identifier

**Belgian
Bibliography**

3. link KBR-data to Wikidata

ISNI as bridge identifier

- ▶ swiftly compare KBR data with data from other trustworthy sources
- ▶ clean & enrich records with info from other sources on same ISNIs
- ▶ e.g. since 2020, we have almost tripled the number of persons identified as Belgians in the KBR catalogue

How to access ISNI data?

The ISNI International Agency releases all data under a Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication:

- via the [ISNI-database](#)
- via ISNI [Web Search Interface](#) or ISNI [SRU API](#)
- via downloadable data dumps, refreshed every 6 months
- formats: html, RDF/XML and JSON-LD

More information? <https://isni.org/page/linked-data/>

How to obtain ISNIs via Wikidata?

ISNI

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P213>

The screenshot shows the Wikidata Query Service interface. At the top left is the Wikidata logo. To its right is the text "Wikidata Query Service" and a button labeled "Examples". Below this is a query editor with a blue information icon on the left. The query text is as follows:

```
1 SELECT ?itemlabel ?isni WHERE
2 {?item wdt:P213 ?isni}
```

Short URL to query: <https://w.wiki/6muj>

1631973 results in 12366 ms

Many thanks!

Any questions?